

AI4

eosc

WP4 Final implementation report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable outlines the final state of the different components and functionalities developed, operated and integrated within WP4 during the whole AI4EOSC project activities. In the present document all the services and functionalities carried out by WP4 are described as part of the AI4EOSC second release (AI4EOSC 2nd Release).

Both architecture and final implementation are presented and discussed for each component such as the workload management system, the PaaS orchestration and provisioning, the AI as a service system, the advanced tools for AI including federated learning, distributed learning and incremental learning, and finally the CVAT tool for image labeling together with CI/CD techniques implementations defined in collaboration with WP5.

1 - INTRODUCTION

1.1 - OBJECTIVES

During the last year of the AI4EOSC project, activities have been continued to improve components and functionalities of the AI4EOSC platform to be provided to the final users. Initially collected and described in the deliverable D4.1 [[AI4EOSC-D4.1](#)], deliverable D4.2 [[AI4EOSC-D4.2](#)] describes the work carried out on each of them, as well as the deviations from the initially defined plan. The deliverable D4.3 [[AI4EOSC-D4.3](#)], reported a status update of the services and tools that has been included in the AI4EOSC 2nd Release. The deliverable D4.4 [[AI4EOSC-D4.4](#)], instead, reported the infrastructure components, and related updates, of the tools developed by WP4 that are part of the AI4EOSC 2nd Release.

The present deliverable reports the final status of the services and tools, providing an overview of the functionalities of the services that are part of the AI4EOSC 2nd Release.

The document is structured as follows.

In [Section 2](#) the final implementation of the infrastructure tools and components has been presented together with a description of each component.

In [Section 3](#) the conclusions are drawn.

1.2 - ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

This section provides an overview of the architectural updates of the related components developed by WP4. In particular the present deliverable will address updates related to the following macro components (see [Figure 1](#) for details):

- PaaS orchestration and provisioning,
- AI as a Service,
- AI4EOSC platform related components.

[System Context] AI4EOSC Platform
Thursday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 1: C4 diagram of the AI4EOSC platform²

2 - FINAL IMPLEMENTATION OF THE WP4 COMPONENTS

In the present section we report an overview of the improvements carried out about technologies and solutions chosen for each of the components. In addition, in [Figure 2](#)

² Original figure:

https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#ai4eosc_view

the architecture of the platform together with its components and their relations is presented, highlighting the WP4 tasks involved.

Figure 2: AI Platform as a Service components and interactions with the other components of the project

2.1 - PaaS ORCHESTRATION AND PROVISIONING

The PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning functionalities are provided via a set of services whose description and interactions are depicted in [Figure 4](#). The following functionalities have been implemented and are part of the second AI4EOSC release (AI4EOSC 2nd Release).

[Container] PaaS Orchestration and provisioning
 1/26/2024, 10:25:04 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 4: PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning components³

The INDIGO-PaaS Orchestration and provisioning service leverages on different micro-services that are described in deliverable D4.4 [AI4EOSC-D4.4] and depicted in [Figure 5](#).

³ Original figure:
https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#orchestration_container_view

Figure 5: INDIGO-PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning micro-services. Details about each component are provided in Deliverable D4.4.

The PaaS Orchestration and provisioning component enables the automatic deployment of different services that have been implemented by means of a TOSCA [TOSCA] template and Ansible Roles⁴, developed by CSIC, UPV and INFN. The TOSCA template provides a standardised blueprint for the deployment of Nomad and Consul, while the Ansible roles automate the configuration of the infrastructure provisioned through the Infrastructure Manager [IM] and the INDIGO-PaaS Orchestrator [INDIGO-PaaS Orchestrator]. This ensures that the deployment process is fast, reliable, and repeatable, reducing the risk of errors and minimising the time and effort required for the deployment. In addition, the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure service for the PaaS components layer is provided by the INDIGO Identity and Access Management Service [INDIGO-IAM] (INDIGO-IAM) that leverages the OpenID Connect and OAuth2.0 [OIDC, OAuth2.0] protocols.

A complete list of TOSCA templates has been made available in deliverable D4.4 [AI4EOSC-D4.4], with a complete description of the templates and the implementation of the deployed services.

Among the list of TOSCA templates there are those related to the automatic deployment of the core components of the Workload Management System, such as Nomad [Nomad] and Consul [Consul], and the core components of the AI4EOSC platform: AI4-PAPI and the AI4EOSC Dashboard.

Moreover, the Ansible roles have been designed to be used not only by the TOSCA templates but also manually for a site administrator who wants to manually deploy the set of virtual resources and then apply the Ansible roles to configure the site to start a new cluster or joining an existing federation.

⁴ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-ansible/>

As a particular use case, two different implementations are described hereafter: the deployment of a Nomad + Consul cluster and the deployment of a site that will join an existing federation.

Deployment of a Nomad + Consul cluster

The deployment of the service in a federated environment is fully managed via the TOSCA template (both from IM and PaaS Orchestrator, see deliverable D4.4 [A14EOSC-D4.4] for more details).

Thanks to the support of the graphical interface provided by the dashboard, the user can fill the parameters to properly deploy and configure the Nomad cluster (see [Figure 6](#) for details). The configuration parameters provided are then passed to Ansible for the cluster configuration. The dimension of the Nomad cluster depends on the resources made available by the federated resource provider.

Figure 6: View of the Nomad configuration from the INDIGO-PaaS Dashboard.

The deployment process starts with the definition in the TOSCA template of a set of input values that enables users to specify the parameters to tune their own deployment: the number of server nodes, the number of working nodes, if some of the working nodes require a GPU or a public IP, the version to install of Consul and Nomad, and other input specifications. The recipe also enables specifying if other components of the platform will be deployed or not, as Traefik or the AI4-PAPI and the AI4EOSC Dashboard, if not set, a plain Nomad + Consul cluster will be deployed. In case of deploying the AI4EOSC components, to enable the user to login to the dashboard also a set of values of an OIDC authentication system must be provided. The deployment of these components is made available for Nomad jobs inside the cluster using Traefik to expose the application endpoints; furthermore, these endpoints are configured to get TLS certificates automatically using Let's Encrypt [LetsEncrypt] CA.

Join resources to an already existing Nomad production cluster

Expanding an existing Nomad federation by adding a new datacenter requires a coordinated process that combines infrastructure provisioning, network configuration, certificate management, and automated deployment. This process builds upon the same Ansible-based framework used for deploying the initial cluster, as described in the previous section.

In this case, the TOSCA template to join an existing federation requires a set of additional fields to be filled (see [Figure 7](#) for details): the IP address and the name of the primary datacenter of the Consul server to join, and a URL to download the Consul certificates and tokens needed to securely join the federation.

In addition, the set of Ansible roles provides an automated way to produce the file with the set of certificate and token files needed to enable a site to join the federation, making the process of site addition easier.

This approach ensures that all federation members are deployed according to a consistent and secure model, reducing complexity and enabling seamless collaboration across sites. By building on a shared Ansible-based automation framework, the integration of new datacenters into the federation remains scalable, repeatable, and maintainable.

The screenshot displays the 'IM Dashboard' interface, specifically the 'Nomad Data' configuration tab. The dashboard header includes navigation links for 'Server Features', 'WNs Features', 'GPU WNs Features', 'Pub WNs Features', 'Nomad Data', and 'Cloud Provider'. The user profile 'Miguel Caballer' is visible in the top right corner. The configuration form contains the following fields and controls:

- 'Launch Traefik job as reverse proxy': A dropdown menu set to 'False'.
- 'Consul version to install': A text input field containing '1.19.2'.
- 'Nomad version to install': A text input field containing '1.9.1'.
- 'Nomad datacenter name': A text input field containing 'ifca-ai4eosc-new'.
- 'Nomad domain name': A text input field containing 'ifca-new'.
- 'List of Nomad namespaces': A list of input fields containing 'ai4eosc', 'imagine', and 'tutorials', each with a red delete icon to its right. A '+ Add' button is located below the list.
- 'URL to download the Consul certificates and tokens': An empty text input field.
- 'IP address of the Consul server to join': An empty text input field.
- 'Primary datacenter of the Consul cluster to join': A text input field containing 'ifca-ai4eosc'.

At the bottom of the form, there are 'Submit' and 'Cancel' buttons. The footer of the dashboard shows the copyright notice '© 2020-2025 GRyCAP' and a row of logos for various partners and projects.

Figure 7: View of the Nomad Join configuration from the IM-Dashboard.

2.2 - WORKLOAD MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Federated Cloud Environment

As part of the final implementation of the Workload Management System (WMS) defined in WP4, a federated cloud environment has been successfully deployed, following the guidelines and architecture outlined in the initial implementation plan (D4.1 [AI4EOSC-D4.1]). This environment is based on a combination of Nomad [Nomad] and Consul [Consul] infrastructures, with Traefik [Traefik] acting as load balancer and reverse proxy, providing service discovery and ingress management across multiple data centers.

The deployment process has been fully automated through a set of Ansible recipes maintained in a public repository⁵. These recipes support several operational tasks critical for the lifecycle of the federated infrastructure:

- Creation of a federated cluster from scratch.
- Addition of new sites to an existing federated cluster.
- Update of Consul and Nomad versions across cluster nodes.

At the time of writing, the production cluster manages over 663 CPU cores, 2058 GiB of RAM, and more than 29 GPUs, distributed across multiple sites including IFCA (CSIC), IISAS, INCD and TUBITAK.

Architecture Overview

The federated architecture of the AI4EOSC Workload Management System (WMS, [Figure 3](#)) is designed to integrate multiple, geographically distributed data centers under a unified orchestration and coordination framework.

At the foundation of this system are three core components:

- **Nomad**, which is responsible for workload scheduling and execution.
- **Consul**, which handles service discovery and cluster coordination.
- **Traefik**, which acts as a reverse proxy and load balancer, managing ingress traffic.

⁵ AI4EOSC public repository, <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-ansible>

Figure 3: Consul WAN gossip architecture scheme

Each participating data center operates as a semi-autonomous unit that includes at least one Nomad server and one Consul server. The Nomad servers coordinate task scheduling, while the Consul servers are responsible for maintaining the global view of the system state and enabling coordination across the federation.

Nomad is designed to support heterogeneous workloads (including batch jobs, interactive services, and system-level tasks) and allows flexible definitions of resource constraints, task dependencies, and execution policies. It natively supports containerized applications (e.g., via Docker [Docker]), but can also manage non-containerized workloads.

All Consul clients (agents running on worker nodes) are configured to communicate only with the Consul servers in their own data center (WAN Federation). This localized communication model ensures that each data center can continue to operate independently in case of temporary inter-site connectivity issues. The Consul servers are responsible for propagating relevant information and synchronizing state across data centers, thereby forming a federated control plane.

This architecture allows seamless expansion: new data centers can be integrated into the federation using the automation mechanisms developed in WP4 (via Ansible [Ansible]), without disrupting existing operations.

Auxiliary Services and Maintenance

A set of auxiliary functionalities has been developed to support the operation and maintenance of the Nomad-based WMS:

- **Email Notification Service:** Notifies users when long-queued jobs are finally deployed.
- **Docuum [Docuum]:** Manages disk space by applying an LRU (Least Recently Used) policy to Docker images.

- **Maintenance Jobs:** Periodic tasks are executed to:
 - Empty the trash folder in Docker containers.
 - Remove Nomad jobs that have been dead for a long time.
 - Delete pending jobs that are not in queued, starting, or unknown states.

Access and Abstraction Layer

Direct user access to Nomad, Consul, or Traefik APIs is restricted. Instead, interaction is mediated through the AI4-PAPI component (described in D5.4 [\[AI4EOSC-D5.4\]](#)), which handles authentication, authorization, and exposes a simplified API. This abstraction not only hides the underlying infrastructure but also enables support for advanced features (e.g. sidecar containers, privileged execution) in a transparent manner.

2.3 - AI AS A SERVICE

The pre-trained AI models developed in the project are delivered for inference through OSCAR⁶, an open-source platform built on Kubernetes for event-driven, serverless data processing that enables users to offload model inference to external computing resources. OSCAR is a framework that can be easily deployed on multi-clouds via the Infrastructure Manager (IM), one of the components integrated in the AI4EOSC platform. It executes applications and AI models that are packaged as Docker images on top of an elastic Kubernetes cluster that is able to adapt its size in terms of the number of nodes to the workload. Moreover, OSCAR supports the execution of applications on ARM-based low-power devices, such as Raspberry Pis, enabling serverless computing at the Edge and composing workflows along the computing continuum.

With this component, AI4EOSC users can trigger the execution of their AI models by uploading files to object storage systems like MinIO [\[MinIO\]](#) or dCache [\[dCache\]](#), or by a direct invocation to the service endpoint. The architecture of OSCAR was presented in D3.3, and it is represented using the C4 model in [Figure 8](#).

⁶ OSCAR GitHub repository. <https://github.com/grycap/oscar>

[Dynamic view] OSCAR dynamic view
 Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 8: Architecture of the OSCAR (AI as a Service) framework⁷.

The main execution unit in OSCAR is a *Service*. A service is defined using the Functions Definition Language (FDL), which is a language that facilitates specifying the details of the service in a YAML format. The basic details of a service are:

- The container image of the model we want to run (typically a Docker Hub image, but other repositories can be used).
- The script that launches the execution of the model. For example, for the majority of the models in the AI4EOSC Marketplace, the call to the *deepaas-cli* command.
- The requirements of the model/application: CPU and RAM memory.
- The input and output details regarding the storage services you want to use. For example, for MinIO, which is the default object storage solution used in OSCAR, you need to determine the input and output MinIO buckets to trigger the executions and store the results.

Once we have defined and created the service, the service can be executed following three different approaches:

1. Through **asynchronous** calls: This is the classic *serverless* approach where the functions, or the AI models in this case, are executed as a consequence of an event triggered in a storage system. For example, uploading files to MinIO causes an event that triggers the execution of the service. Once its execution is finished, the results are stored in the same or another MinIO bucket, or even in another storage system, allowing users to create workflows.
2. Through **synchronous** calls: These are the response to an HTTP request that directly calls for the execution of the model with an input payload. This

⁷ Original figure:
https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#oscar_dynamic

approach is recommended if you need to achieve low latency in your execution. These scalable HTTP-based endpoints use Knative [Knative] to perform the synchronous executions in OSCAR and can auto-scale in terms of the concurrent number of containers simultaneously serving the requests.

3. **Exposing** the service: This is used where the AI model already exposes a web interface or a REST API. For example, a trained model with a DEEPaaS API [DEEPaaSAPI] can be made accessible from outside the OSCAR cluster. Once the service is exposed, a user can directly interact with the service bypassing OSCAR's API. Still, OSCAR will be managing the underlying infrastructure, providing autoscaling based on the average CPU within certain user-defined limits. One of the benefits of this approach is for models with large model weights, since these will be loaded just once, thus reducing the load time of model weights, resulting in faster response times. However, the container is always running with allocated computing resources, thus potentially wasting resources if not being used. This is the main difference of this approach from the other two. This approach has been fully implemented during the project's lifetime.

OSCAR provides a graphical web interface, which is the Dashboard, to facilitate its usage. This dashboard is integrated with EGI Check-in and Keycloak. The OSCAR Dashboard has been fully redesigned during the project, as shown in [Figure 9](#).

Name	Image	CPU	Memory	Actions
ai4eosc-uc2-2	jedrzejmok/ai4eosc_uc2	1.0	2.0Gi	> < ✖
ai4eosc-0331cb34-eea5-11ef-bd7c-0242ac1	ai4oshub/ai4os-demo-app	2	3000Mi	> < ✖
cowsay	ghcr.io/grycap/cowsay	1.0	1Gi	> < ✖
flows-maneza-sey8t9j9	ghcr.io/grycap/oscar-flows	1.0	2Gi	> < ✖
juno7e3b98	ghcr.io/grycap/juno	1.0	2Gi	> < ✖
plants	grycap/oscar-theano-plants	1.0	1Gi	> < ✖
plants-classification	ai4oshub/plants-classification	1.0	2Gi	> < ✖
resnet-50	ghcr.io/k1b1/miserver:resnet-50	1.0	2Gi	> < ✖
thermal-detector	ai4oshub/thermal-bridges-rooftops-detector	3.0	4Gi	> < ✖
thermal-detector-test	ai4oshub/thermal-bridges-rooftops-detector	3.0	4Gi	> < ✖
thermal-detector-test-sync	ai4oshub/thermal-bridges-rooftops-detector	3.0	4Gi	> < ✖

Figure 9: Screenshot of the new version of the OSCAR Dashboard.

Moreover, for programmatic access, OSCAR provides a REST API and a Python API to interact with the OSCAR cluster. And for experienced users, OSCAR also provides a command-line client, OSCAR CLI. With the OSCAR CLI you can also manage the life cycle of an OSCAR service, you can apply a FDL service description or manage different OSCAR clusters with the same CLI. It is worth mentioning that it is integrated with EGI Check-in [EGECheckIn] by installing the OIDC agent [IODCAgent].

Below is a summary of the main functionalities implemented during the project for integrating the OSCAR platform within the AI4EOSC platform.

- **Exposed services:** This functionality allows users to deploy services that include their own APIs and/or UIs within the OSCAR cluster, giving users direct access to capabilities like model inference through the DEEPaaS API offered by AI4EOSC models or specific graphical user interfaces.
- **Image fetching:** This capability was added to OSCAR to accelerate the initial executions of the AI models, no matter the internal working node where it is executed inside the OSCAR cluster. Once a service is created in OSCAR, the Docker image of the model to be executed is pre-fetched in each node to be ready at execution time. This allows the system to mitigate the *cold start*, a delay attributed to resource provisioning on the first invocations.
- **Multitenancy support:** OSCAR can serve multiple users based on the use of OIDC, where each user has a unique ID associated with their account on the identity provider used to log in. Currently, the platform supports both EGI Check-in and Keycloak instances as identity providers for authentication. Through the policy management implemented, users can decide the privacy and isolation level of their applications and data, being able to create private services and private buckets that only specified users can access and use.
- **Mounting external storage on service volumes:** This feature enables the mounting of a folder from a storage provider, such as MinIO or dCache, into the service container. This has allowed the implementation of OSCAR Batch [[OSCARBatch](#)], a tool designed to perform batch-based processing using OSCAR clusters. OSCAR Batch includes a coordinator service where the user provides a MinIO bucket containing files for processing. This service calculates the optimal number of parallel service invocations that can be accommodated within the cluster and distributes the image processing workload accordingly among the services. This is mainly intended to process large amounts of files, for example, historical data of an observatory service. It ensures the efficient use of available CPU and memory resources in the OSCAR cluster.
- **Monitoring and accounting support:** A solution based on Prometheus [[Prometheus](#)] and Grafana [[Grafana](#)] has been deployed to monitor the usage of the OSCAR cluster in terms of resources consumed, services deployed, and user details. These metrics are of special interest for the use cases of the project (WP6) and also external use cases of the platform (like iImagine use cases).
- **Integration with AI4PAPI:** The AI4EOSC API can interact with the deployed OSCAR cluster to deploy services and perform inference directly from the AI4EOSC Dashboard. For that, a *generic script* has been developed to allow the creation of OSCAR services. Thus, any DEEPaaS API-compliant model (all of the models in the AI4EOSC catalog) can be deployed effectively, abstracting the complexities of code implementation from the users. As illustrated in [Figure 10](#), users can deploy a model easily in the OSCAR cluster by just a few clicks. More information can be found in AI4Docs [[OSCARDeployModel](#)].

Figure 10: Integration of OSCAR in the AI4EOSC Dashboard.

By the time this deliverable is written, the cluster deployed for the project is based on the OSCAR release [v3.6.2](#), which integrates the previously mentioned functionalities, and the resources have been scaled to leverage some models' requirements.

2.4 - ADVANCED AI TOOLS: DISTRIBUTED AND FEDERATED TRAINING

As described above, the AI4EOSC platform aims to provide users with an environment where they can develop, exploit and adopt their AI based models and applications. In addition, it was essential for us to be able to provide them with enhanced AI tools that can be used easily and intuitively from the platform.

In this sense we have focused on making it simple for users to train models in a federated way. This allows the development of global models with decentralized data without the need to centralize them, thus exploiting distributed resources especially without compromising privacy when it comes to sensitive data. Thus, the architecture of a federated learning (FL) system is composed of a server and multiple clients. Each client has its own data and the server is in charge of orchestrating the whole process. The most common flow is as follows: (1) the clients agree on a common ML/DL model to train; (2) the model is sent to each client; (3) each client trains the model locally with its own data; (4) each client sends to the server the weights/gradients resulting from training the model locally; (5) the server aggregates the received parameters using a predefined strategy and builds a global model; (6) the global model is sent back to the clients. The process is repeated from step (3) for a fixed number of rounds or until the model converges.

In this sense, users can deploy a federated learning server directly from the dashboard using two softwares widely used in the state of the art: *Flower* [Flower] or *NVFlare* [NVFlare]. Additionally, clients can run from other deployments on the platform, operating from local resources of each of them or from external cloud providers. These two software products are available in the platform as tools (see [Figure 11](#) for details).

Figure 11: AI4EOOSC dashboard, tools section. The two FL software products available are framed.

Flower FL server

In order to perform a FL training with Flower [\[Flower\]](#) users can deploy and run a server directly using the dashboard form. For that purpose we are maintaining a fork of the Flower library [\[AI4EOOSC/flower\]](#) in order to support our own extensions, which will be further detailed in the following. First, it is important to note that we decided to maintain such fork to solve an issue concerning running the server behind the *traefik*. Then, users have to complete the following steps for creating the deployment with the server:

- **General configuration:** contains the configuration regarding the deployment options, the service to run, and the docker tag. The different fields to be completed are:
 - **Deployment options:** deployment title (less than 45 characters), deployment description and service to run (fedserver, JupyterLab [\[JupyterLab\]](#) or Visual Studio Code [\[VSC\]](#)). In this step the user can also select if he/she wants to monitor the CO2 emissions of the training.
 - **Docker options:** the Flower federated server is configured with a Bearer token for authentication, allowing the user that is in charge of starting and managing the server to set up authentication tokens so that the clients can authenticate to connect with the server. This functionality is available selecting the docker tag *tokens*, and we have created an extension to the flower library to integrate this functionality, *ai4-flwr* [\[ai4os/ai4-flwr\]](#). This extension allows the creation of a token interceptor using the secrets stored in *Vault* (which has been used as secret management system) for each deployment of the FL server. Such secrets can be created and revoked, and each of them is associated with a unique identifier. This is controlled in a simple way from the AI4EOOSC dashboard (see [Figure 12](#)).

fl-server

List of secrets

client1			
client2			
client3			
client4			
default			

Items per page: 5 1 – 5 of 5 < >

New secret name*

Figure 12: Secrets management from the AI4EOSC dashboard for authenticating with the Flower FL server.

- **Hardware options:** although the server does not require particularly demanding hardware specifications (since the main computational workload is performed on the client side), in this step the user can select the number of CPUs, RAM, and disk storage.
- **Federated configuration:** in this step the users can introduce the configuration parameters needed for the FL server including:
 - Minimum number of clients available.
 - Minimum number of clients for fitting the model.
 - Number of rounds of the training.
 - Evaluation metric(s), which can be selected from a list or manually.
 - Privacy enhancing techniques:
 - Users can apply differential privacy during the aggregation process (which is integrated in Flower), and they can select from the dashboard the noise multiplier, the clipping norm and the number of clients sampled for that purpose.
 - In addition, we have integrated a new feature that allows users to apply metric privacy during the aggregation, following the work done in [\[fl-metricdp\]](#). In order to integrate this functionality we have created a new class which inherits from a pre-fixed Flower strategy, *MetricDifferentialPrivacyServerSideFixedClipping*. This class is introduced in the fork of the library available in the AI4EOSC GitHub community [\[AI4EOSC/flower\]](#), in the script *metricdp_fixed_clipping.py* within *src/py/flwr/server/strategy*. This new class is an extended version of the class *DifferentialPrivacyServerSideFixedClipping* from Flower in such a way that a new function is added for dynamically calculate in each round the maximum distance between the different pairs of models, and thus apply the notion of metric privacy in FL

established in [\[fl-metricdp\]](#). Both this functionality and global differential privacy addition can be controlled from the dashboard (see [Figure 13](#)).

Configure training: **Federated learning with Flower**

Tools / Federated learning with Flower / Deploy Show help

General configuration Hardware configuration Federated configuration

Federated options

Number of rounds 5	Evaluation metric accuracy
Number of minimum clients (fit) 2	Number of minimum clients (available) 2
Federated aggregation strategy Federated Averaging (FedAvg)	

Privacy options Differential privacy

Metric privacy false	Noise multiplier 1
Number of sampled clients 2	Clipping norm 0.1

Back Submit

Figure 13: Flower FL server configuration from the AI4EOSC dashboard, including privacy options.

NVFlare FL server

In this case, users can deploy directly from the platform (see [Figure 14](#)) an NVFlare dashboard that allows them to get startup kits for initializing the process and perform a secure connection of the components of the FL system (FL servers, FL clients and admin clients), including the configuration files and certificates required for establishing secure communication between them. In order to deploy this dashboard the administrator only needs to introduce their NVFlare credentials (email and password) in the dashboard and select the starting and end date for the training setup. In addition, they will be able to access a JupyterLab environment for the server. Through the dashboard the admins can register new sites/clients and manage them (see the options available in the NVFlare dashboard, including the startup kits in [Figure 15](#)).

Configure training: **Federated learning with NVFlare**

Tools / Federated learning with NVFlare / Deploy Show help

General configuration Hardware configuration NVFlare configuration

NVFlare options

Username* test@ai4eosc.eu	Password* *****
Make project public false	Docker image registry.services.ai4os.eu/ai4os/ai4os-nvflare-client:2.5-Stifo
Starting date 05/08/2025	End date 06/08/2025

Figure 14: NVFlare configuration from the AI4EOSC dashboard.

Figure 15: NVFlare dashboard deployed from the AI4EOSC platform. From the “Downloads” section the server startup kit can be obtained. From the panel on the right the admin can manage the clients, as well as configure the project and the server.

The integration of these two software products in the platform and the search to provide users with simple ways to carry out their FL training has been reflected in the numerous online tutorials carried out on the subject. In particular, the ones presented in [Table 1](#) stand out and can be used as reference for using these two tools.

Table 1: List of tutorials concerning FL performed within the scope of the AI4EOSC platform.

Title	Type	Link
Tutorial: Federated Learning in AI4EOSC	Video. Long tutorial	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FrqVummLNbU&list=PLynvTSH6JZ9qR4pybDfYaekYt8cBhpuLG
AI4EOSC short tutorial: Federated learning via the platform	Video. Short tutorial	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_wc1AUB5JyM
AI4OS docs: Flower	Tutorial/guide	https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/federated-flower.html
AI4OS docs: NVFlare	Tutorial/guide	https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/howtos/train/federated-nvflare.html
Federated Learning in the EOSC	Webinar	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v7blpOB92C8

The integration in the form of a tool includes deployment of the NVFlare server and NVFlare Dashboard. The current integration provides NVFlare version 2.5, utilizing a fork [\[AI4EOSC-NVFlare\]](#) of the official release that includes extended support for long Fully Qualified Domain Names (FQDNs). Additionally, a client container image [\[AI4EOSC-NVFlare-Dockerfile\]](#) is provided out of a box, featuring TensorFlow [\[TensorFlow\]](#), in particular v2.13.0, and JupyterLab for advanced interactive inspection, development and experimentation. This image serves also as an example of client image definition. The NVFlare integration extends the PAPI and includes the implementation of a Nomad job specification [\[NVFlare-Nomad\]](#). This integration enables automated provisioning and deployment of an NVFlare federated learning server and the NVFlare Dashboard, facilitating client management within a federation with minimal user intervention. The NVFlare integration supports multiple independent NVFlare deployments within the AI4EOSC platform. This is achieved through a set of Traefik routing rules that leverage Server Name Indication (SNI) to differentiate between different deployments, while leveraging common ingress ports for administration (8003) and federated learning (8002).

2.5 - INTERACTIVE DEVELOPMENTS TOOLS

Interactive Development Environment

The Interactive development environment (IDE) tool offers application developers a prototyping environment with access to computing resources. The IDE consists of pre-built Docker images that include packages simplifying the development and integration with the AI4EOSC platform, like a Python programming environment, DEEPaaS API, and rclone, and offer one of the JupyterLab or VS Code environments that most of the developers are familiar with. These images are based on the official Docker builds for one of the deep learning frameworks, such as Tensorflow or Pytorch, or featuring the NVIDIA CUDA toolkit, or Ubuntu OS. All IDEs come with integrated support for running on GPUs. The process of creating pre-built AI4EOSC IDEs is automated via Jenkins pipeline. Users can also profit from the snapshot feature provided by the platform, allowing them to back up running IDE deployments and restore them later. Additional info is provided in D5.5 [\[AI4EOSC-D5.5\]](#).

Modules Template

The Modules Template service is composed of two complementary components: (i) the “Templates Hub”, an online platform that streamlines the generation of new AI4EOSC-compatible modules (see [Figure 16](#)); and (ii) the AI4EOSC platform “Modules” section, which enables users to deploy development environments, AI services or applications (see [Figure 17](#)).

Figure 16: Templates Hub front page with main project cookiecutters

The Templates Hub reduces integration time of projects to the platform by wrapping curated Cookiecutter-based [Cookiecutter] templates into a web form that users can easily complete. Each template exposes a controlled set of variables defined by the AI4EOSC template maintainers (Cookiecutter configuration), which the user must complete to personalise the generated project base.

These user-supplied values are validated (type, format, allowed choices) and are simultaneously (i) injected throughout the generated file and directory structure and (ii) consolidated into a standardized metadata file consumed later by the platform for catalog discovery, filtering and deployment orchestration. Users then select a template (e.g. minimal or advanced) and, once the form is completed (see Figure 18), obtain a ready-to-build project as a ZIP archive. Each generated module includes a harmonized directory structure (e.g. source skeleton, Dockerfile, API endpoint, tests, metadata, CI/CD workflow and licensing) to ensure fast and consistent integration into the platform.

Internally, the service executes Cookiecutter in an isolated, ephemeral workspace, validating and sanitizing all parameters and packaging results without persisting user code or secrets. By enforcing a common scaffold and embedding best practices (containerization, test harness, metadata, CI/CD hooks), the service reduces setup time, lowers human error and facilitates subsequent automation steps such as continuous integration (Jenkins [Jenkins AI4EOSC]/ GitHub Actions [GitActions]) and deployment through AI4-PAPI, Nomad and OSCAR. Reproducibility, metadata & provenance: each generated module embeds the standardized metadata file (task type, framework, resource hints, license, authors, version, keywords, base image reference), supporting FAIR principles (findability, interoperability, reusability) and enabling later reconstruction of the original scaffold and traceability of changes.

AI4OS Template (minimal) ★★★★★ [Source](#) [python](#) [ai4os](#) [ai4eosc](#)

Simple, minimal template, with the minimum requirements to integrate your code in AI4OS platform

AI4
eosc

Filling this web-form will generate a .zip file with the folders generated by the cookiecutter.

Short name of your project (max 4 words). The GitHub repository name and python module name are derived from the project_name.

Author name(s) (and/or your organization/company/team). If many, separate by comma

E-Mail(s) of main author(s). If many, separate by comma

A short description of the project.

Figure 17: Form example to customize project generation and metadata

Once the Python project is completed, users submit a pull request to the modules catalog repository for review⁸. After validation by platform administrators, the module is published and becomes visible on the platform’s front page⁹.

Modules

AI4EOSC External catalogs: AI4Life

Search Additional filters 0 Sort: By name By most recent 44 result(s) found

Libraries Tasks Platform Categ... Data Types Tags Add filter

<p> 2D semantic segmentation</p> <p>2D semantic segmentation trained on the Vaihingen dataset</p>	<p> 2D semantic segmentation multilabels with Unet</p> <p>Semantic segmentation with Unet Deep Learning model applied to segment Cercospora Leaf Spot.</p>	<p> ai4os-demo-app</p> <p>A toy application for demo and testing purposes. We just implement dummy inference/training, ie. we return the same inputs we are fed. The module does not contain any AI code.</p>	<p> Apple tree blossom image segmentation</p> <p>We suggest a 2D image segmentation model based on UNET algorithm to segment images with blossoming apple tree</p>
<p> Artistic Style Transfer</p> <p>A module to apply artistic style transfer using Pytorch.</p>	<p> audio_vessel_classifier</p> <p>Classifies the distance to the nearest vessel from a 10-second underwater audio recording using a deep learning model.</p>	<p> Bird sound classifier</p> <p>Classify audio files among bird species from the Xenocanto dataset.</p>	<p> Body pose detection</p> <p>Detect body poses in images.</p>

Figure 18: AI4EOSC platform displaying multiple available modules and filters.

The “Modules” section of the AI4EOSC platform then provides an interface to filter and discover modules using their metadata (task type, framework, resource requirements, keywords) and to act on them through several lifecycle operations:

⁸ Ai4os catalogue, <https://github.com/ai4os-hub/modules-catalog>

⁹ Organization entry point: <https://github.com/ai4os-hub>

This integrated workflow—templates, review, catalog publication and multi-mode deployment—accelerates the path from concept to a reproducible and maintainable AI service within the AI4EOSC ecosystem.

CI/CD environment

Several adjustments and improvements have been made to the CI/CD of the different AI4EOSC components.

For different reasons, in particular the adoption of already existing CI/CD tools, during the project lifetime two CI/DC tools have been adopted: GitHub Actions and Jenkins.

Adopting CI/CD practices through tools like GitHub Actions and Jenkins significantly enhances software development efficiency and reliability.

Thanks to the seamless integration with repositories, GitHub Actions have been massively adopted for the INDIGO PaaS Orchestration components, enabling automated testing, building, and deployment workflows directly within the development lifecycle of each PaaS component. More information about the GitHub Actions and the CI/CD integration is provided in deliverable D7.3 [[AI4EOSC-D7.3](#)] where the link to the CI/CD is provided for each component.

Jenkins, instead, is providing a robust, customizable automation server that supports complex pipelines and integrations across diverse environments and has been adopted for the rest of the AI4EOSC components and all user applications on the AI4EOSC marketplace. In such respect, more information is provided in deliverable D5.5 [[AI4EOSC-D5.5](#)].

CVAT

The core of the CVAT [[CVAT](#)] integration into the AI4EOSC platform is a Nomad job specification¹⁰, which has been developed by adapting the original Docker Compose orchestration file¹¹ of the CVAT v2.28.0 (released on 2025-02-06). The Nomad job ensures the correct configuration and deployment of all the original fourteen CVAT containers as individual Nomad tasks, their isolation from other CVAT instances, and networking configuration by setting Traefik rules. Advanced analytics and monitoring features based on Vector, ClickHouse, and Grafana are also included ([Figure 19](#)). Additionally, it incorporates four AI4EOSC-specific tasks—*share*, *synclocal*, *syncremote*, and *backups*—to extend CVAT functionality (see [Table 2](#)).

Modifications [[CVAT1](#)] to CVAT included configuration adjustments, automated superuser provisioning, and enhancements to the original Dockerfile to incorporate the `rclone` [[rclone](#)] tool, enabling seamless integration with Nextcloud remote storage. Corresponding updates were also made to the AI4EOSC Platform API to ensure the compatibility with the CVAT Nomad job specification. The integration process underwent multiple iterations, beginning with CVAT version 2.7.3, progressing through 2.25.0 and culminating in version 2.28.0.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-papi/blob/master/etc/tools/ai4os-cvat/nomad.hcl>

¹¹ <https://github.com/cvat-ai/cvat/blob/v2.28.0/docker-compose.yml>

In relation to the planned persistence enabler, an alternative approach was adopted due to performance and caching issues encountered when mounting remote storage as local volumes. Instead, a less network-intensive, shutdown-triggered full backup mechanism was implemented. This solution performs a complete backup of the active CVAT instance and uploads it to a designated backup directory on the remote storage. The implementation adheres to the official CVAT backup procedure [CVAT2], with full automation integrated into the process. The use of remote storage as locally mounted volumes has not been entirely deprecated; rather, it is utilized specifically for the shared path [CVAT3] configuration in CVAT.

Beyond the scope initially defined in D5.3, an automated periodic backup mechanism [CVAT4] was implemented for CVAT to enable regular backups of projects and annotations. This complements the shutdown-triggered full backup process by providing more frequent data protection. Additionally, a proof-of-concept [CVAT5] was developed to demonstrate the feasibility of integrating CVAT with custom annotation models deployed as services within the OSCAR framework.

The integration of CVAT into the AI4EOSC platform has been validated through testing with users from both the AI4EOSC and iImagine [iImagine] projects.

Figure 19. Grafana Dashboard for analytical data on CVAT utilization. This Dashboard opens after clicking on "Analytics" in the main CVAT screen.

Table 2: Additional CVAT services by AI4EOSC.

Nomad task name	Description
share	Enables seamless access to Nextcloud remote storage by mounting volumes as local paths within task containers.
synclocal	Restores the CVAT instance from a backup stored on remote storage.
syncremote	Creates a backup of the CVAT instance on remote storage upon shutdown.
backups	Performs periodic backups of CVAT projects and associated annotations.

The **syncremote** task automatically generates a snapshot backup of the entire CVAT deployment upon system shutdown and transfers it to a remote storage location using rclone, as configured during the deployment process (e.g., Nextcloud). During the initialization of a new CVAT instance, a previously stored snapshot may be selected for restoration. The selected snapshot is retrieved from the designated remote storage via the **synclocal** task into the allocated instance. During this process, the superuser credentials are replaced with the values specified in the Dashboard configuration (see [Figure 20](#), “Snapshot Configuration”). All available snapshots are queried from the remote storage when the corresponding dropdown menu is opened. The implementation of snapshot creation adheres to the official CVAT backup procedure [\[CVAT2\]](#), with full automation integrated into the process.

Figure 20. CVAT deployment configuration in the AI4EOOSC Dashboard

Furthermore, the remote storage is also mounted as a local volume and utilized by CVAT to serve as the shared path [\[CVAT3\]](#). [Figure 21](#) illustrates the remote shared folder in the Nextcloud web interface and its corresponding mount as a shared path in the CVAT dashboard.

Figure 21. Data prepared for annotation in Nextcloud (left) and the corresponding data accessible in the “Connected File Share” section of CVAT for import (right).

The **backups** task utilize CVAT API to create backup of projects or annotations, and cron for scheduling the backups. It includes a sweeper program to automatically clean obsolete backups and thus save storage space. The sweeper can be configured to keep the minimal number of backups and to keep the backups for a minimal period of time while considering the maximum number of backups. Within the AI4EOSC platform, the periodic backup system has been configured as described in [Table 3](#). The implementation of the periodic backup system with all the configuration options explained is available in its GitHub repository [[CVAT6](#)].

Table 3: Periodic backup of CVAT configuration.

Parameter	Value	Description
CVAT_BACKUP_TTL_HOURS	24	minimum age of backup file in hours; if the age of the backup file exceeds this value and there are more than $\$(CVAT_MIN_NUM_BACKUPS)$ backup files, this backup is deleted by the sweeper
CVAT_MIN_NUM_BACKUPS	3	minimum number of backup files to keep regardless of their age ($\$(CVAT_BACKUP_TTL)$)
CVAT_BACKUP_SAVE_IMAGES	false	whether to store images along with annotations
CVAT_BACKUP_REQUEST_TIMEOUT_HOURS	1	maximum time in hours to wait for CVAT to prepare a backup

Additional modifications [[CVAT1](#)] were required also to CVAT [[CVAT7](#)] itself. These included configuration adjustments, automated superuser provisioning, and enhancements to the original Dockerfile to incorporate the rclone [[rclone](#)] tool for integration with Nextcloud remote storage.

3 - CONCLUSION

The present document reports the final status of the tools and services developed within the AI4EOSC projects' activities. The services, included in the AI4EOSC 2nd Release, are deployed in production on the AI4EOSC platform.

In particular, the final implementation of the infrastructure tools and components has been presented in **Section 2**, where a description of each component, together with its interoperability with the other components, has been provided and described.

In general, the activities proceeded as expected from the initial plan in order to have all the components ready and the related functionality included in the AI4EOSC 2nd Release.

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